

New data on the subfossil fauna from “Forum Serdica” (Sofia City, Bulgaria; 3rd-19th century AD)

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Abstract: Presented are the results of the excavations in the central Sofia circus of 3rd-4th to 16-19th c. AD from 2016, deposited over the Roman “Forum Serdica”. They number 8313 bone/shell finds of 47 taxa (at least 36 species and domestic forms) of invertebrates (mollusks – land snails and freshwater mussels) and vertebrate animals (bony ray-finned fishes, birds and mammals /incl. man/). One species, the Aurochs, is globally extinct and 1 disappeared from the recent fauna of Bulgaria (Great bustard). Seven species are listed in the country’s Red Data Book: European carp, Great bustard, Eurasian lynx, Gray wolf, Red deer, Brown bear, and Wildcat.

Keywords: Medieval animal husbandry and hunting, Last Aurochs on the Balkans, Late-medieval poultry, Means of livelihood in the Ottoman period of Sofia

Introduction

The continuation of the “Forum Serdica” project (Archaeological excavations and exploration of “St Nedelya Circus”) revealed a lots of new archaeozoological materials in 2016. It remains unexamined and unpublished, as the previous study of BOEV (2016) covered the animal remains only of 2015. The new excavations, as before, were carried out by the Sofia Municipality by the same team of the National Archaeological Institute and Museum of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NAIM-BAS), led by Assist. Prof. Dr. VESELKA KATSAROVA.

Material and Methods

The handed animal remains (October 2016) for archaeozoological examination numbered 8313 pieces of bone/dental fragments and mollusk shells (Table 1). They were identified through the osteological collections of the National Museum of Natural History at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Department of Vertebrate Animals).

The material provided was collected in a total of 367 collections/samples in 2016 and according to its date was divided into 3 groups: (1) antiquity – 3rd-4th c. AD, (2) late antiquity – 4th-6th c. AD (more often 5th-6th c. AD) and (3) Ottoman period – 16th-19th c.

AD (more often 17th-19th c. AD). When collected, the materials of a total of 37 collection samples were dated as “mixed”. The chronological distribution of each species/sample is given in Table 1. The finds from the Ottoman period make up the vast majority (over 85%) of the material. All avian bone material (562 findings) has been inventoried in the Fossil and subfossil birds collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NMNHS-BAS): No 16820; 16833; 17056-17057; 17170; 17197; 17229; 17302-17860). In addition a small part of the mammalian finds (lynx, brown bear) have been deposited in the mammalian osteological collections of the museum.

General composition of the established wild and domestic vertebrates

The species composition is rather varied. The examined bone, teeth and shell remains belong to 47 taxa (at least 36 species and domestic forms) of invertebrates (mollusks) – land snails (Fig. 1) and freshwater mussels (Fig. 2) and vertebrate animals (bony ray-finned fishes /Actinopterygii/, birds and mammals /incl. man/) (Table 1).

A significant part of the collected remains because of their bad and fragmentary preservation is inappropriate for taxonomic determination. A total of 3649 finds (43.9 %) represent unidentifiable frag-

Table 1. Animal representation in the collected archaeozoological material from “Forum Serdica” (pr. Sofia City) in 2016

No	Taxa	English Name	Total number of finds	Number of processed finds	Number of burnt finds
MOLLUSCA					
Gastropoda					
Heterobranchia					
1	<i>Helix lucorum</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Turkish snail	17		
	Total		17		
Bivalvia					
Unionoida					
2	<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788	Thick shelled river mussel	1		
	Total		1		
OSTEYCHTHYES					
Siluriformes					
3	<i>Silurus glanis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Wels catfish	1		
	Total		1		
Cypriniformes					
4	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> Linnaeus, 1758	European carp	1		
5	Cyprinidae fam. indet	Cyprinid fishes	2		
	Total		3		
	Bony fishes total		4		
AVES					
Anseriformes					
6	<i>Anas platyrhynchos domestica</i>	Domestic duck	12		3
7	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Mallard	5		
8	<i>Anser anser domestica</i>	Domestic goose	123	2	9
	Total		140		
Ciconiiformes					
9	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i> Linnaeus, 1758	White stork	4		
	Total		4		
Galliformes					
10	<i>Gallus gallus domestica</i>	Domestic hen	410	3	84
11	<i>Pavo cristatus domestica</i>	Domestic peafowl	3		
12	<i>Perdix perdix</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Grey partridge	2		
	Total		415		
Accipitriformes					
13	<i>Buteo buteo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common buzzard	1		
	Total		1		
Otidiformes					
14	cf. <i>Otis tarda</i> Linnaeus, 1758	?Great bustard	1		
	Total		1		
Passeriformes					
15	<i>Corvus cornix</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Hooded crow	1		
	Total		1		
	Birds total		562		
MAMMALIA					
Erinaceomorpha					
16	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i> Barrett-Hamilton, 1900	Northern white-breasted hedgehog	4		
	Total		4		

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	English Name	Total number of finds	Number of processed finds	Number of burnt finds
Rodentia					
17	<i>Rattus rattus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)/ <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> (Berkenhout, 1769)	Black rat/ Brown rat	1		
	Total		1		
Lagomorpha					
18	<i>Lepus europaeus</i> (Pallas, 1778)	European hare	25		
19	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	European rabbit	11		
	Total		36		
Carnivora					
20	<i>Ursus arctos</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Brown bear	1		
21	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Red fox	19		
22	<i>Canis familiaris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Domestic dog	65		
23	<i>Canis lupus/familiaris</i>	Grey wolf / Domestic dog	9		
24	<i>Meles meles</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	European badger	2		
25	<i>Lynx lynx</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Eurasian lynx	1		
26	<i>Felis silvestris</i> Schreber, 1777	Wildcat	16		
27	<i>Felis catus/silvestris</i>	Domestic cat / Wildcat	1		
28	<i>Felis catus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Domestic cat	33		
29	<i>Felis cf. catus</i>	?Domestic cat	3		
30	<i>Canis lupus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Gray wolf	32		
31	<i>Canis cf. lupus</i>	Gray wolf	2		
	Total		184		
Artiodactyla					
32	<i>Sus scrofa domestica</i>	Domestic pig	322	6	11
33	<i>Sus scrofa scrofa</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Wild boar	242		4
34	<i>Capra hircus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Domestic goat	881	5	2
35	<i>Ovis aries</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Domestic sheep	518	7	7
36	Ovicaprinae	Small ruminants	203		3
37	<i>Bos taurus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Domestic cattle	1328	20	6
38	cf. <i>Bos taurus</i>	?Domestic cattle	33		
39	<i>Bos primigenius</i> (Bojanus, 1827)	Aurochs	10		
40	<i>Bos cf. primigenius</i>	?Aurochs	29		
41	<i>Bos taurus/primigenius</i>	Domestic cattle / Aurochs	47		
42	<i>Cervus elaphus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Red deer	48		
43	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	European roe deer	66		
	Total		3727		
Perissodactyla					
44	<i>Equus ferus caballus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Domestic horse	63	2	2
45	<i>Equus africanus asinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Domestic donkey	34		
46	<i>Equus cf. asinus</i>	?Domestic donkey	1		
	Total		98		
Primates					
47	<i>Homo sapiens</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Wise man	30		
	Total		30		
	Mammals – bone splinters		3649		6
	Mammals total		7729		
	Vertebrates total		8295	45	137
	Animal remains total		8312	45	137

Fig. 1. *Helix lucorum*: shell.
(Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 3. *Silurus glanis*: os frontalis ad. (Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 2. *Unio crassus*: shell.
(Photo: Z. Boev)

ments (s. c. bone splinters) without preserved diagnostic features for their osteological identification.

Partly unidentified are also 203 bone fragments, listed as “small ruminants, Ovicaprinae”– sheep/goat; Table 1.).

Fishes and fishing

Three species of bony fishes at least have been recorded (Table 1). The Welsh catfish (Fig. 3) occurs in the lower and middle reaches of the large rivers (KARAPETKOVA, ZHIVKOV, 1995). Similarly, at present the European carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) is spread in the Danube River and the lowermost reaches of its larger tributaries (KARAPETKOVA, ZHIVKOV, 1995).

Domestic animals and animal husbandry

Among the new materials from 2016, the composition of the farmed domestic animals again is

rather varied. Domestic animals are represented by 13 forms – cattle, goat, sheep, pig, horse, donkey, rabbit, dog, cat, as well as the chicken, goose, duck, and peacock (Fig. 4, 5). “Forum Serdica” is the second site of *Pavo cristatus* in Bulgaria. So far this valuable decorative bird was known only from the Roman town of Nicopolis-ad-Istrum (4th-6th c. AD; BOEV, BEECH, 2007). The present 3 finds (leg bones) originated from deposits of 17-19th c. AD.

Domestic chicken dominates (410 finds), followed by domestic goose (123) (Table 1).

A total of 4080 animal finds (49.18 % of all vertebrate animals remains) belonged to domestic animals, i. e. almost half of the collected finds. In addition 57 bones (0.69 %) have been incompletely identified both as belonging to wild or corresponding domestic forms.

The cattle was most commonly spread domestic animal. Its remains have been uncovered in 256 of the total 367 samples from the excavations. A small brachycerous breed (Fig. 6) was most commonly bred. Here we do not present special measurements of numerous finds, but the conclusion about predominant small (and brachycerous) cattle breed is undoubtfull. The domestic goat was present at 133 samples, and domestic sheep – in 99 samples.

The collected new material (as that of 2015) confirms practicing of 3 main livelihoods – fishing, hunting and animal husbandry. We also could add and fourth one – gathering, as we have found shell remains of gathered freshwater river mussel and land snails, widely used for food resources until recently.

The animal husbandry was divided into avi-

Fig. 5. *Pavo cristatus domestica*: NMNHS 17 625 tarsometatarsus dex. ♀ sad. (Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 4. *Pavo cristatus domestica*: NMNHS 17 405 tarsometatarsus sin. ♂ ad. (Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 7. *Rattus rattus/norvegicus*: incisivum ad. (Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 6. *Bos taurus*: skull of a brachycerous specimen ad. (Photo: Z. Boev)

culture, cuniculture, as well as pig-breeding, cattle (stock)-breeding, horse- and donkey-breeding, and dog- and cat-breeding. As in the material of 2015, the domestic rabbit is rare – only 11 bones of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* have been collected.

It is undisputedly proven by the material that the hen has been represented by at least 3 breeds,

based on bone size measurements. At least 10.5% of the finds are referred to the so-called “bantam” breed – small non-meat (more often decorative) breeds, slightly larger than a domestic pigeon. Very large hens are very rarely presented, and the most widely distributed breed is a medium-sized breed. The donkey was 2 times less bred than the horse.

Fig. 8. *Bos taurus* (above) and *Bos primigenius* (below): compared cranial fragments with horn shafts (Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 9. *Lynx lynx*: left mandible (Photo: Z. Boev)

Fig. 10. *Cervus elaphus*: cut antler ad. (Photo: Z. Boev)

Wild animals

The wild fauna is represented by some valuable hunting mammals and birds, as well as of some species of uncertain direct significance to man as Black/Brown rat (Fig. 7), Northern white-breasted hedgehog, as in the material of 2015). The presence of the White stork could be explained by the species' aptitude to synanthropization since ancient times.

The same could be the reason for the record of the Hooded crow.

One species, the Aurochs (Fig. 8) is globally extinct since 1627, and one other, the Great bustard is disappeared as breeding species in the country since 1970-s. The finds of the Aurochs deserve special attention. According Prof. NIKOLAY SPASSOV (NMNHS – Sofia) at least some of the bones of 16th-19th century could be referred to a large primigene breed of cattle, showing almost undistinguishable osteometric features as the Aurochs. In general, we also do not exclude completely such a probability, but we consider it rather impossible. As *B. primigenius* was established in the material of 2015-2016 in the same site (BOEV, 2016) and the surviving of the Aurochs until 16th century in Bulgaria in other site – Veliki Preslav (only 290 km from Sofia) and the presence of large suitable habitats on the CW Bulgaria (present Kyustendil, Pernik and Sofia Regions) the possibility of surviving of the Aurochs must not be excluded.

The found mandible of lynx (Fig. 9) is an extremely important record of this disappeared (1941)

and reappeared (2008) rare carnivore. “Forum Serdica” is the 11th site in Bulgaria where subfossil finds of *L. lynx* are found. It is dated Late Medieval Ages (16th-19th century AD) (BOEV, 2017).

Data of 2016 also confirm the wide diversity and richness of the wild fauna in the Sofia region. The remains of Aurochs again confirm our statement (BOEV, 2016) for the last Aurochs in Bulgaria from Sofia region. Present finds originated from two different sections of the excavated area of different dating: (1) late antiquity (3rd-4th c. AD) and (2) late medieval (16th-19th c. AD).

Seven species are now endangered or vulnerable in the Bulgarian nature. They have been listed in the country's Red Data Book: European carp, Great bustard, Eurasian lynx, Gray wolf, Red deer, Brown bear, Wildcat.

Large carnivores are well represented. Besides species mentioned above, the red fox and European badger are also established among the remains.

The five aquatic species (Thick-shelled river mussel, European carp, Wels catfish, White stork, and Mallard) suggests a large water body with open surface. We remind that at present both rivers, Perlovska and Suhodolska lie at a distance of only ca. 2 km (see Boev, 2016).

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Traces on bones

The trace analysis shows that 45 bones bear traces of cutmarks (complete cuts – cutting off) or only cutmarks (Table 1). In addition 137 bones show evident traces of burning, i. e. the all are completely or partially burnt.

Most often burning traces could be noticed on chicken bones (84), but also meat of some other animals, e. g. domestic ducks, geese, pigs, goat, sheep, and even horses, had been roasted.

We have found cut antlers of the Red deer, which were cut through a saw (Fig. 10) for secondary utilization of their antlers. Analogous processing was also found for the horns of some adult rams and he-goats.

In general 137 bones (1.65 % of the finds) bear traces, left by man.

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Златозар БОЕВ

(Резюме)

Представени са резултатите от археологическите разкопки през 2016 г. на централния площад на София („Св. Неделя“) от 3-4 до 16-19 в. н. е., отложени върху „Forum Serdica“. Материалът наброява 8313 останки от 47 таксона (най-малко 36 вида и домашни форми) от безгръбначни (мекотели – сухоземни охлюви и сладководни миди) и гръбначни животни (костни риби, птици и бозайници /вкл. и човешки останки/). Част от находките на извънредно едри бовиди са отнесени към изчезналото диво говедо (тур) – допускане заради отнасянето на всички останали останки от домашни говеда към дребни брахицерни породи. Един вид (голямата дропла) е изчезнал (като гнездещ) от съвременната фауна на страната. За 7 вида от „Червената книга на Р България“ се допълват сведенията за тяхното разпространение в миналото: европейски шаран, голяма дропла, евроазиатски рис, сив вълк, благороден елен, кафява мечка и дива котка.

Установено е, че на пряк огън (опичане) е било приготвяно за храна месото на домашни патици, гъски, кокошки, свине, кози, овце и дори и коне. Рогата на някои животни (благородни елени, домашни кози) са били отсичани с брадва или отрязвани с трион за вторичната им употреба.